

Inactivation of a wild isolated *Klebsiella pneumoniae* by photo-chemical processes: UV-C, UV-C/H₂O₂ and UV-C/H₂O₂/Fe³⁺

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1 **Abstract**

2 Shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) farming is an important economic activity in several
3 countries . Pathogens in shrimp farms and its effluents pose a potential hazard for both
4 humans and shrimps. Wild strains of bacteria were characterized in a shrimp farm, and
5 *Klebsiella pneumoniae* was chosen as a good indicator due to its presence in the pond and
6 the effluent and its resistance to antibiotics. Different photochemical processes (UV/H₂O₂,
7 UV/H₂O₂/Fe³⁺) were tested for inactivation of wild isolated *K. pneumoniae* and compared
8 to UV-C radiation. By kinetic modelling, a k_{\max} equal to 0.43 s⁻¹ was obtained for UV-C
9 treatment. After optimizing the cited processes, ranging [H₂O₂]: 10-30 mg·l⁻¹; an optimal
10 [H₂O₂] of 10 mg·l⁻¹ was found, increasing k_{\max} on 13.63% compared to UV-C. This optimal
11 concentration was tested for UV/H₂O₂/Fe³⁺ process; ranging [Fe³⁺]: 2-20 mg·l⁻¹. The highest
12 yield was obtained by a [H₂O₂]:[Fe³⁺] = 10:2, which leads to 4-Log reduction in 12.88 s of
13 treatment. Moreover, resistance of *K. pneumoniae* was compared to *Escherichia coli*. The
14 latter proved to be more sensitive despite its similar cellular structure. Results suggested that
15 the photochemical processes could enhance disinfection efficiency, especially for photo-
16 assisted Fenton-like process in most resistant bacteria.

17 **Keywords**

18 Aquaculture; Iron; Antibiotic resistance bacteria; Fenton process; Advanced oxidation
19 processes; Hydrogen peroxide.

20

21 **1 Introduction**

22 Globally, aquaculture accounts for almost 50% of fish destined for food and is the fastest
23 growing food sector [1]. More than 550 aquatic species are currently grown around the
24 world. Within these species, shrimp (*Litopenaeus vannamei*) and its cultivation is an
25 important economic activity in several countries, such as China [2], Thailand [3], Vietman
26 [3], India [4,5], Brazil [6] and Costa Rica [7] is one of the most important economic activities
27 in Ecuador [1].

28 Ecuadorian shrimp exports increased from \$1,278 to \$2,580 million dollars between 2012
29 and 2016, when they were the third most exported product, representing 15% of the country's
30 exports [8]. With an exponential growth, shrimp farms amounted to about 210,000 hectares
31 in 2016 along the four coastal provinces of Ecuador (El Oro, Guayas, Manabí and
32 Esmeraldas). In the province of El Oro, in southern Ecuador, shrimp farming has contributed
33 to improving the socio-economic situation of the region. However, shrimp farms take up
34 large areas of mangrove, estuaries and coastal bays and provoke a remarkable environmental
35 impact in areas with great environmental value.

36 The high concentrations of shrimp, fecal matter and unconsumed organic fertilizers favor
37 the growth of pathogenic microorganisms, which are an important source of disease and
38 mortality in shrimps, causing economic losses [9]. Those pathogens are normally prevented
39 by the extensive use of antimicrobials, leading to the presence of multiple resistant bacteria
40 in the cultured shrimps, including cited pathogens, making the control of them extremely
41 challenging [10]. Effluents from this activity are released into the surrounding aquatic
42 environment and, as a consequence of that, aquaculture activities appears among one of the
43 main sources of Antibiotic Resistance Bacteria (ARB) in the environment, considered as
44 contaminants of emerging concern [11], posing a potential ecosystem deterioration and
45 health hazard [12,13].

46 Thus, water treatment technologies, especially for disinfection purposes, are needed in order
47 to assure water quality for increasing process efficiency and generating safe discharges to
48 natural environment. Several disinfection techniques are available, like chemical
49 disinfectants and antibiotics. However, these methods proved to be insufficient against
50 resistant pathogens not guaranteeing complete disinfection [14]. Sodium hypochlorite
51 (NaClO) is a common disinfection chemical because of its low cost and high effectiveness.

52 Nevertheless, chlorination could generate potentially harmful chloro-organic by-products
53 when natural organic matter is present [15].

54 Ultraviolet (UV) irradiation is a well-established treatment that disinfects without by-
55 products due to absorption of UV by organic molecules, such as DNA [16–18]. However,
56 microorganisms are capable of repairing themselves [19,20]. UV irradiation efficiency can
57 be enhanced by generating radicals (mostly hydroxyl radical, •OH) with several catalysts
58 (TiO₂, Iron) or oxidants (H₂O₂, O₃) that can be photo-activated. •OH is a powerful oxidizing
59 agent with a short lifetime that lacks the potential for environmental damage [21]. Processes
60 in which •OH is involved are called Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOPs) [22,23] and are
61 capable of inactivating microorganisms by degradation of the chemical structure of cell walls
62 [24].

63 Some of these UV-based technologies have been studied as alternatives to marine water
64 disinfection treatment: UV/TiO₂ [25,26], UV/O₃ [27,28], etc. However, TiO₂ requires
65 catalyst cleaning [25] and O₃ generates by-products [17]. Thus, the use of H₂O₂ appears to
66 be a promising alternative.

67 The photolysis of H₂O₂ generates •OH following Eq. (1) [22]. Iron, in conjunction with H₂O₂
68 and light, acts as a catalyst and increases the production of •OH in an AOP known as photo-
69 assisted Fenton process. This is a cyclic catalytic process that generates •OH transforming
70 Fe³⁺ to Fe²⁺ and vice versa. Depending on iron source, it is so-called Fenton-like reaction
71 (Fe³⁺). Among different AOPs, the photo-assisted Fenton process has attracted great
72 attention due to its high generation of •OH. The process can be summarized in Eq. (2) and
73 (3) [15,29].

77 UV/H₂O₂ and photo-Fenton (UV/H₂O₂/Fe^{2+,3+}) processes are both effective at disinfection
78 in both natural water and wastewater [30–32]. Even though there were doubts of the
79 effectiveness of these treatments for seawater disinfection because of the high concentration
80 of inorganic ions, which can interfere by •OH scavenging in AOP applications [22,33,34],
81 some authors have already demonstrated effectiveness [15,35,36].

82 In this context, the main objective of this work is to identify and isolate pathogenic
83 microorganisms present in effluents from shrimp farms located in southern Ecuador and
84 evaluate the inactivation efficiency of different processes: UV-C, UV-C/H₂O₂ and UV-
85 C/H₂O₂/Fe³⁺ by using two different strains: a wild isolated bacterium from a shrimp farm
86 (*Klebsiella pneumoniae*) and a typical microbial indicator (*Escherichia coli*).

87 **2 Materials and methods**

88 **2.1 Water sampling**

89 In order to identify and isolate different microorganisms present in shrimp farm effluents,
90 water samples were collected from a shrimp farm located in Huaquillas canton (3°28'52.97"
91 S 80°14'36" W), El Oro province, southwestern Ecuador. The climate of this area is warm
92 and dry with a temperature of 20 to 35°C throughout the year.

93 Three sampling points were selected in the shrimp farm (influent, pool and effluent). Each
94 water sample was collected in 20 liter plastic drums. The samples were transported at 4°C
95 and in the dark to the laboratory of the Department of Chemistry and Exact Sciences of the
96 Universidad Técnica Particular de Loja. Additionally, water characterization
97 (microbiological and physico-chemical) was performed in each sampling point (Table S1.
98 Suppl. data).

99 **2.2 Bacterial isolation and identification**

100 **2.2.1 Bacterial isolation**

101 In order to isolate different microorganisms, water samples were filtered twice. Firstly, three
102 liters of sample were filtered with Whatman No. 1 filter paper to remove plant residues and
103 sediments. Secondly, they were filtered on a 0.45 µm membrane filter (Neogen Filter). Five
104 milliliters of alkaline peptone (APA Merck KGaA, pH 8.5) culture medium were added to
105 the membrane-containing residue and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. Samples were
106 cryogenically preserved (-75°C) after resuspending in 900 µl of the culture medium with 100
107 µl of dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO 10%).

108 Isolation and purification of microorganisms were carried out from the cryogenic reserves
109 following the quadrant streak technique over a series of commercial media: APA agar, blood
110 agar, MacConkey agar, TCBS and GSP agar. Finally, the plates were incubated at 37°C for
111 24 hours. Colonies with good morphology were extracted and spread over the same media

112 where initially isolated. The purity of the cultures was reviewed by macroscopic analysis on
113 agar plates (shape and color of colony) and microscopic examination of the developed
114 colonies (wet amount and Gram staining) [37]. Additionally, the occurrence of some
115 commonly used biochemical markers was identified by means of oxidase (cytochrome c
116 oxidase), catalase (catalase enzyme produced by organisms that live in oxygenated
117 environments) and indole (tryptophanase system) tests. The oxidase test is a key test to
118 differentiate between the families of Pseudomonadaceae (ox +) and Enterobacteriaceae (ox
119 -) [38].

120 **2.2.2 Bacterial identification**

121 Molecular identification was carried out through DNA extraction (Pure Link™ Genomic
122 DNA mini Kit) by the protocol for Gram-negative or Gram-positive bacteria, according to
123 the manufacturer's specifications. The partial 16S rDNA was amplified using universal
124 primers 27F 5'-AGAGTTTGATCMTGGCTCAG-3' [39] and 1492R 5'-
125 GGTTACCTTGTTACGACTT-3' [40]. The PCR products were purified with the Wizard®
126 SV gel and PCR Clean-Up System kit, and the presence of amplicons was verified by
127 GelRed® stained (Biotium, Hayward, CA, USA) in 1% agarose electrophoresis gels. All the
128 purified products were sequenced by Macrogen (Seoul-Korea).

129 The sequences obtained were compared to the closest reference sequences available in the
130 GenBank database (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/>). In addition, our sequences and
131 the closest sequences from the database were aligned using the MAFFT software (G-INS-I
132 strategy) in order to build the phylogenetic trees for each group of bacteria. The phylogeny
133 was generated by Maximum Likelihood (ML) analysis implemented in the MEGA v5
134 software.

135 **2.3 Inactivation assays**

136 **2.3.1 Microbiological procedures**

137 Among the microorganisms detected and isolated, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* cultures were
138 chosen as indicator bacteria. First, from a cryogenic reserve, an aliquot of 0.1 ml was taken
139 to incubate over Tryptic soy broth (BD soybean broth, pH 7.3±0.2) at 37°C for 12-14 hours.
140 After this, the inoculum was adjusted to 0.5 McFarland with a densitometer (Grant
141 instrument, DEN-1) and, finally, 1 liter of water matrix was inoculated with the culture in a
142 ratio 1:10 to adjust to a final concentration of ca. 10⁷ CFU·ml⁻¹.

143 *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922®) was used as control strain for its prevalence in waste
144 water. It was seeded over Violet Red Bile Agar (BD-Difco) and inactivated under the same
145 conditions given above for *K. pneumoniae* to compare the effectiveness of the different
146 treatments.

147 After inactivation assays, 10 ml aliquots were transferred into sterile tubes from the reactor
148 outlet and seeded over trypticase soy agar (BD-Difco, pH 7.3±0.2). The number of colony
149 forming units per milliliter (CFU·ml⁻¹) was quantified by colony counting. To do this, 100
150 µl of each aliquot from every treatment were spread with a sterile L-shaped Drigalski loop
151 until the medium absorbed it completely. Petri plates were inverted and incubated at 37°C
152 for 24 hours. This procedure was performed in duplicate and only measurements with a
153 coefficient of variation fewer than 30% were considered. In case the count was very high,
154 appropriate dilutions were made until obtaining an optimum count (10-100 CFU). The
155 bacterial suspension was quantified before adding to the reactor, by the same technique, to
156 assure an inoculum of 10⁷ CFU·ml⁻¹. Control samples were performed in each assay to assure
157 that bacterial concentration did not change during experimental procedures.

158 **2.3.2 Experimental assays**

159 The inactivation experiments were carried out using a continuous reactor consisting of a
160 peristaltic pump feeding system (Cole-Parmer Master Flex L/S Digital Drive Model 7523-
161 80) with a central UV-C lamp (6W – Low Pressure Hg) in a tube of quartz and stainless steel
162 with a plastic shell (Ultraviolet Sterilization Filter, Model: OPP-625, Microfilter Co. Ltd.).
163 Irradiated volume was 140 ml with a mean intensity of 16.7 µW/cm².

164 Three treatments were performed: UV, UV/H₂O₂ and UV/H₂O₂/Fe³⁺. Chemicals used were
165 H₂O₂ (30% by weight, Merck) and Fe³⁺ (Iron(III) chloride hexahydrate, Merck, ACS). In
166 order to optimize different processes, different concentrations of H₂O₂ and Fe³⁺ were
167 evaluated according to Table 1. Water matrix for experimentation was prepared by
168 dissolving NaCl (Merck, ACS) at 35 g·l⁻¹ Milli-Q water. H₂O₂ and Fe were measured in
169 some assays before and after the treatment with peroxide tests for H₂O₂ (colorimetric test
170 strips method, 0.5–25 and 1–100 mg/L H₂O₂ Merckoquant–Merck) and flame atomic
171 absorption spectrometry (Perkin Elmer AAnalyst 400) for Fe, finding no consumption

172 Table 1. Experimental design for evaluation of different inactivation processes for *E. coli*
 173 and *K. pneumonia*.

Treatment	H ₂ O ₂ (mg·l ⁻¹)	Fe ³⁺ (mg·l ⁻¹)	Retention time (s)
UV	0	0	
UV/H ₂ O ₂	10	0	16, 26, 36, 46, 56
	30	0	
UV/H ₂ O ₂ /Fe ³⁺	10	2	
	30	6	

174

175 2.4 Data treatment

176 Inactivation of bacteria is represented as the logarithm of the ratio between the number of
 177 bacteria after a time *t* of exposure in the reactor and the number of initial bacteria. The
 178 GinaFiT software, a plug-in for Microsoft Excel, was used to find which mathematical model
 179 best fits the data obtained and to calculate inactivation kinetics, k_{\max} (s⁻¹) [41]. Only those
 180 kinetics which explanatory mathematical model obtained a coefficient of determination (R^2)
 181 greater than 0.9 were accepted.

182 SPSS version 20 was used to carry out a normality test (Shapiro-Wilk) as a preliminary step
 183 to ANOVA analysis to verify whether there were significant differences in bacteria
 184 inactivation between the treatments used (UV, UV/H₂O₂, UV/H₂O₂/Fe³⁺) according to the
 185 experimental design shown in Table 1.

186 3 Results and discussion

187 3.1 Bacterial identification

188 Four microorganisms were initially purified over different culture media. Morphological
 189 analysis of bacteria was used only to determine the purity of the cultures but molecular
 190 analysis was crucial to identify the species.

191 Molecular analysis showed four species, confirming Gram-negative and Gram-positive
 192 bacteria (Table 2). Only two strains were defined to species level, and two were defined to
 193 genus level due to the lack of species information in the GenBank database. The BLAST
 194 sequence identifications were supported by maximum likelihood in the phylogenetic trees
 195 for each genus (trees not shown) with bootstrap values >80% by clade.

196 **Table 2.** Bacterial identification in water samples from the shrimp farm. Percentages of
 197 similarity are between our new sequences and the sequences available from the GenBank
 198 database.

199

Strains code	Identification		Similarity	Query cover	Accession number
	Gram-definition	BLAST			
PAMR	Gram-negative	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	99%	100%	LC216325
FPAC	Gram-negative	<i>Vibrio fluvialis</i>	99%	100%	KT163389
PAAS	Gram-positive	<i>Bacillus</i> sp.	99%	100%	KJ473716
FPAN	Gram-positive	<i>Exiguobacterium</i> sp.	100%	100%	KX911472

200 *K. pneumoniae* was isolated after growing on MacConkey agar as a mucoid, convex and
 201 lactose positive colony, and it showed the characteristics of a Gram-negative bacteria after
 202 Gram staining and was indole negative, oxidase negative, catalase positive. *K. pneumoniae*
 203 was isolated from the water collected inside the pond and in the effluent of the pond.

204 *Vibrio fluvialis* was isolated after growing on TCBS agar as medium-sized, smooth, yellow
 205 colonies and displayed the characteristics of a Gram-negative, motile bacterium. It was
 206 indole negative, oxidase positive. *V. fluvialis* was isolated from the influent of the pond.

207 *Bacillus* sp and *Exiguobacterium* sp. were isolated over Alkaline Peptone agar (APA
 208 medium) as small convex colonies, *Exiguobacterium* sp. revealed a characteristic orange
 209 appearance on the plate and it was a rod-shaped Gram-positive bacteria. *Bacillus* sp.
 210 exhibited an opaque appearance in pale yellow and dry colonies, and it was a rod-shaped
 211 Gram-positive bacterium after gram staining. *Bacillus* sp was isolated from the water inside
 212 the pond whereas *Exiguobacterium* sp. was isolated from the influent of the pond.

213 The presence of microorganisms in the influent, such as *V. fluvialis*, *Bacillus* sp and
 214 *Exiguobacterium* sp., could be explained by wastewater discharges in the area from the city
 215 of Huaquillas. In this case, *K. pneumoniae* would also be expected to be present.

216 In contrast to the other strains identified, *K. pneumoniae* was the only one detected in both
 217 pond and effluent samples, suggesting that this bacterium is more resistant to the antibiotics
 218 used by the farmers than the rest of the microorganisms identified. *K. pneumoniae* is
 219 considered a problematic pathogen and could be a significant risk in both human health and
 220 shrimp production [32,42]. Furthermore, it has special defense mechanisms against different
 221 bactericides and antibiotics [43,44]. Thus, AOPs are especially interesting for *K.*

222 *pneumoniae* inactivation in shrimp farms. Further research will be carried out to inactivate
223 the rest of the isolated bacteria.

224 3.2 Inactivation assays

225 In order to evaluate the disinfection efficiency of several UV-based processes for treatment
226 of aquaculture effluents, different inactivation assays were performed with wild bacteria
227 isolated in Section 3.1 (*K. pneumoniae*) as a microorganism indicator. Results were
228 compared with a typical indicator, *Escherichia coli* (ATCC 25922®), as shown in Figure 1.
229 Plate counting afforded a detection limit of 2 CFU·ml⁻¹.

230

231 **Figure 1.** Inactivation profiles of *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* under several
232 disinfection processes. Symbols represent the average of experimental points and lines show

233 a fit by Log-linear + tail model: (I) ●UV-C; (II) △ UV/H₂O₂, [H₂O₂]=10 mg·l⁻¹; (III) ▲
234 UV/H₂O₂, [H₂O₂]=30 mg·l⁻¹; (IV) □ UV/H₂O₂/Fe³⁺, [H₂O₂]=10 mg·l⁻¹, [Fe³⁺]=2 mg·l⁻¹; (V)
235 ■ UV/H₂O₂/Fe³⁺, [H₂O₂]=30 mg·l⁻¹, [Fe³⁺]=6 mg·l⁻¹ DL: Detection Limit

236

237 Inactivation of bacteria is shown in Figure 1 as logarithmic reduction of the surviving
238 bacteria vs. retention times in the UV-reactor. Experimental raw data were fitted into Log-
239 Lineal + tail model ($R^2 > 0.9$), according to Eq. (4) [45].

$$240 \quad N_t = (N_0 - N_{res}) \cdot e^{-k_{max} \cdot t} + N_{res} \quad \text{Eq. (4)}$$

241 Where N represents the concentration of viable bacteria, in CFU·ml⁻¹, at a given time (N_t)
242 and before treatment inactivation (N₀); fraction related to the tailing phenomenon (N_{res}); k_{max}
243 is the inactivation rate of the Log-linear + tail model (s⁻¹) and “t” is the retention time (s) in
244 the UV-reactor.

245 According to the results obtained, *K. pneumoniae* was observed to be more resistant than *E.*
246 *coli*. For *E. coli*, 4 log-reductions (99.99%) were reached in only 16 s of exposure to all
247 treatments studied: UV-C (I), UV/H₂O₂ (II, III) and UV/H₂O₂/Fe³⁺ (IV, V). In the case of *K.*
248 *pneumoniae*, higher retention times were needed to reach 4 log-reductions: UV/H₂O₂ and
249 UV/H₂O₂/Fe³⁺ achieved it with 26 s of exposure to UV light. The treatment exclusively with
250 UV light required 36 s to achieve the same degree of inactivation.

251 A deeper analysis, based on k_{max} (s⁻¹) was performed for different processes applied in
252 order to detect significant differences in inactivation kinetics between *K. pneumoniae* and
253 *E. coli*. Results are shown in Figure 2.

254

255 **Figure 2.** Kinetic rate constant, k_{max} (s^{-1}), obtained in different disinfection processes for
 256 *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Escherichia coli*. Error bars depict the standard deviation.
 257 Asterisks (*) show data for differences ($p < 0.05$) between bacteria (*K. pneumoniae* - *E. coli*)
 258 in the same treatment. Capital letters show significant differences ($p < 0.05$) between
 259 treatments for *K. pneumoniae* (A–B) and lowercase for *E. coli* (a–e). I.e. treatments with the
 260 same letter have no significant differences among them, compared to treatments with
 261 different letters, between which there are significant differences.

262 It was detected that the inactivation was always greater for *E. coli*, suggesting a major
 263 sensitivity of this bacterium compared to *K. pneumoniae*. The origin of the strain could be
 264 relevant; while *E. coli* is a commercial strain, *K. pneumoniae* has been isolated from the
 265 wild. Also, cell wall structure has a significant role in UV-light processes: when UV is
 266 applied, genetic material and proteins are the main biomolecules affected, principally
 267 because of the high absorption caused by pyrimidine bases [46]. Sensitivity also depends on
 268 cell wall characteristics (Gram-positive or –negative) [47,48]; however, *E. coli* and *K.*
 269 *pneumoniae* are both Gram-negative bacteria, with the same cell wall structure.

270 *E. coli* shows high sensitivity to UV light alone; e.g., some authors, [25,49], reached rapid
 271 inactivation of this organism at short exposure times. Others, [50], reported more resistant
 272 properties for *K. pneumoniae* than *E. coli*. Hijnen et al. [16] compared the resistance of
 273 different microorganisms, including bacteria and bacterial spores. Their study suggested an
 274 increased UV-resistance for wild strain bacteria. Apart from the nature of the strain, it was

275 reported that *K. pneumoniae* has a special mechanism against bactericidal processes, such as
276 large cell aggregations or production of extracellular polymers [43,44].

277 When H₂O₂ is added to the UV-C process, the photolysis of H₂O₂ generates •OH which
278 enhance the disinfection efficiency. Nevertheless, H₂O₂ overload brings a recombination
279 phenomenon and consequent scavenging of •OH, reducing disinfection yield [51]. To avoid
280 H₂O₂ in excess, two different concentrations were tested (II, III). Previously, several
281 concentrations over 30 mg·l⁻¹ were tested but no significant differences in disinfection were
282 found. In this sense, inactivation efficiency of *E. coli* improved (p<0.05) by adding H₂O₂ to
283 a water matrix, showing a better yield at the higher concentration of H₂O₂ (III, 30 mg·l⁻¹)
284 than at the lower (II, 10 mg·l⁻¹). It is probably due to the major reaction capacity of the
285 generated •OH which has a strong effect on cell inactivation.

286 Nonetheless, the same effect was not observed for *K. pneumoniae*. Since the kinetic rate
287 constant is higher by adding H₂O₂ (in comparison with UV alone), no significant differences
288 were detected with 10 and 30 mg·l⁻¹ of H₂O₂ (II, III). As previously noted, *K. pneumoniae*
289 has a robust capsule that can protect it from direct attacks from oxidant radicals. *E. coli*,
290 however, showed high sensitivity to UV light alone, especially at high intensities [52,53]; it
291 could enhance the inactivation caused by the generation of •OH [25,49]. Moreover, the slight
292 effect that H₂O₂ might cause by diffusion mechanisms into the cell could generate an extra-
293 effect due to the intracellular iron and could explain those differences [14,15,32,54]. Those
294 results are in agreement with previous studies [49].

295 By adding Fe³⁺, the inactivation yield improved (*E. coli*) compared to treatment I, II and III;
296 mainly at high concentrations (V). We could assume, as explained previously, that the
297 enhancement of disinfection yield could be due to the UV-C sensitivity of this bacterium,
298 accentuated by the presence of oxidants, rather than the impact of •OH itself [25,49].

299 For *K. pneumoniae*, results differ as with I, II, and III processes. The inactivation rate is
300 improved again by adding Fe³⁺, although the cited improvement is only significant (p<0.05)
301 for treatment IV which has been the most efficient treatment and the only treatment that
302 showed significant differences with the rest.

303 In the photo-assisted Fenton-like process, different concentrations have been tested: 10, 30
304 mg·l⁻¹ H₂O₂ together with 2, 6 mg·l⁻¹ of Fe³⁺, respectively. Disinfection efficiency improved
305 significantly when low concentrations were applied (IV), i.e., the effect of the iron catalyst
306 is enhanced at 10 mg·l⁻¹ of H₂O₂ instead 30 mg·l⁻¹. It can corroborate the optimum

307 concentration of $10 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$ of H_2O_2 for both UV/ H_2O_2 and UV/ $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2/\text{Fe}^{3+}$ processes within
308 the concentrations tested because of optimal radical generation and avoidance of
309 recombination processes. As a result, an iron-catalyzed process on *K. pneumoniae* has a
310 significant effect on cell inactivation

311 It is known that ferric salts catalyze the generation of $\bullet\text{OH}$ in the so-called Fenton-like
312 reaction. In this case, radicals are generated by reduction of Fe^{3+} to Fe^{2+} , mainly by H_2O_2
313 and light-assisted processes [55,56]. Even though many studies reflect the major efficiency
314 of Fe^{2+} as the starting iron species compared to Fe^{3+} [32], the natural form of iron is mostly
315 as Fe^{3+} which encourages assessing Fe^{3+} efficiency and its potential as a source of iron. . On
316 the same way, it has to be taken into account that this process with Fe^{3+} is limited by pH,
317 which tends to precipitate at near neutral values. Moreover, since the Fenton-like process
318 seems to be light-dependent (unlike the Fenton process) [57], the use of UV-C as a source
319 of light could enhance the disinfection efficiency. Despite these assumptions, a disinfection
320 mechanism based on cell adsorption could explain the enhancement of the process: Fe^{3+} has
321 high charge density, and it can be attracted by bacterial cells; so the oxidizing radical's
322 formation close to the cells may cause membrane damage which, together with the H_2O_2 in
323 solution that increases permeability of the membrane (because of diffusive processes), could
324 be the reasons for those disinfection improvements [57]. Spuhler et al. [57], demonstrated
325 that most Fe^{3+} was retained together with the bacterial pellets when it was filtered, indicating
326 that Fe^{3+} , in some circumstances, could be more effective than Fe^{2+} in solution.

327 In this study, the use of Fe^{3+} together with H_2O_2 and UV-C light significantly improved the
328 inactivation. These results are in agreement with previous studies in which virus [58] or
329 bacteria [44,57] are target organisms. In these studies, inactivation efficiency with Fe^{3+} and
330 natural iron in solution was enhanced, compared to UV and/or UV/ H_2O_2 processes..

331 Another important factor for AOPs application is the composition of the water matrix. In
332 this study, a synthetic water matrix based on distilled water and NaCl in high concentrations
333 similar to seawater ($\approx 35 \text{ g}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$) has been used. Such chloride concentrations can interfere
334 with disinfection processes by scavenging $\bullet\text{OH}$ and generating inorganic radicals ($\bullet\text{Cl}$ and
335 $\bullet\text{Cl}_2$) that could be less reactive [34]. The slight improvements with *K. pneumoniae* when
336 H_2O_2 is added can be attributed to this scavenging effect of salts. However, those salinity
337 effects seem to be small. For example, Penru et al. [33] achieved full disinfection in seawater;
338 Moreno-Andres et al. [22] obtained efficiency losses of 5.22% compared to distilled water.
339 Our results suggest a slight improvement (13.63 %) in kinetic rates for *E. coli* and *K.*

340 *pneumoniae* compared to UV-C. In real water matrices other ions and organic matter could
341 be present in solution and interfere with disinfection processes. This is the case of Br⁻ and
342 HCO₃⁻ in marine waters which have a strong scavenging rate that could lead in decrease
343 disinfection efficiency [15,22,34]. Because of that, in further studies should be determined
344 the weight of this scavenging and/or generation of other kind of radicals.

345 Fenton processes in water with high chloride content can be affected as well by formation
346 of chloro-Fe³⁺ complexes (FeCl⁺, FeCl²⁺, FeCl²⁺) which could decrease the generation of
347 •OH and consequently lower the efficiency [59]. On the other hand, Spuhler et al. [57]
348 reached high disinfection efficiencies, even in saline solution. Rubio et al. [15] significantly
349 improved disinfection in artificial seawater under a photo-Fenton process. In our case, in the
350 best situation (IV), an increase in kinetic rate constant (*K. pneumoniae*) of 50% has been
351 achieved compared to UV-C and 44.4% compared to UV/H₂O₂.

352 **4 Conclusions**

353 Among different bacteria isolated in shrimp farms, *K. pneumoniae* was chosen as
354 microbiological indicator for evaluation of different UV-based processes because it was the
355 only bacteria identified in both the pond and the effluent. Compared to *E. coli* as typical
356 microbial indicator, higher resistance was detected for *K. pneumoniae* in all processes tested.
357 it is the best indicator for both AOPs evaluation of disinfection in this context and a good
358 ARB indicator/model.

359 Considering inactivation kinetics, an optimal concentration of 10 mg·l⁻¹ within the
360 concentrations tested was obtained for the UV/H₂O₂ process; the same was obtained for
361 UV/H₂O₂/Fe³⁺, which was the most efficient treatment for the inactivation of *K. pneumoniae*
362 among those tested. Those processes can improve the disinfection efficiency (based on k_{max})
363 by 13.63% and 50% respectively, compared to UV-C radiation. The increase in H₂O₂/Fe³⁺
364 concentrations did not always result in an increase in efficiency.

365 According to the results obtained, despite the possible effects caused by chlorides; the
366 application of AOPs could enhance disinfection efficiency, especially for photo-assisted
367 Fenton-like process in most resistant bacteria.

368 **Acknowledgments**

369 This research has been developed under PROY_QUI_123, funded by UTPL; and R+D
370 Project AVANTE (CTM2014-52116-R) funded by the Spanish Ministry of Economy and
371 Competitiveness. Javier Moreno-Andrés thanks the CEI CamBio mobility program
372 (Universidad Internacional de Andalucía - Resolución Rectoral 49/2014 de 29 de abril).

373 The authors acknowledge the chemistry and exact sciences department for providing the
374 facilities to carry out the experiments and for all the support provided. Especially to Monica
375 Cisneros, Diego Maza, Miguel Guamán, Mercedes Villa and Valeria Fárez. The authors also
376 thank Gyselle Jaramillo, Daniela Valarezo and Thalia Diaz for their support with the
377 experiments and Chris Brinegar for revising the translation into English.

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